

Rejection Sensitivity as a Predictor of Perceived Loneliness: A Gender based Study

Gurleen Kaur Bajwa, Asha Chawla Thakral, and Deepika Vig

Department of Human Development and Family Studies, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab

The present research aimed to study rejection sensitivity as a predictor of perceived loneliness among 460 adolescents, 230 of whom were girls and 230 were boys. Sample was randomly selected from Government Senior Secondary Schools of three districts namely Ludhiana, Patiala and Sangrur in the Malwa region of Punjab. Data were gathered using a self-structured socio-personal information sheet, Fear of Rejection Scale (Nafees & Jahan, 2018) and Loneliness Scale (Hamid & Parvez, 2020). The results revealed that girls demonstrated higher levels of fear of rejection, exhibiting higher sensitivity towards rejection and people-pleasing, whereas boys had more social isolation and a sense of emptiness, which highlighted greater feelings of loneliness. Overall loneliness and fear of rejection showed significant gender differences, with boys reporting higher feelings of loneliness than girls. Rejection sensitivity and loneliness were found to be significantly positively correlated, which suggested that a greater fear of rejection was linked to more social isolation, emptiness, distressed reaction and overall loneliness among both genders, although the effect was more noticeable in some areas for boys.

Keywords: Rejection sensitivity, perceived loneliness, adolescents

Adolescence is characterised by increased emotional sensitivity and acceptance becomes a psychological necessity. Long-term effects on mental health and general well-being might result from even minor indications of rejection at this delicate period. Rejection entails being excluded from social contact or relationship. (DeWall and Bushman 2011). Rejection Sensitivity (RS) is the term used for those individuals who become too sensitive to rejection and as a result, develop a fear of rejection in general (Pietrzak et al., 2005). Cassidy and Shaver (2016) asserted that early childhood connections have a major impact on the development of rejection sensitivity. A child's sensitivity to social rejection is likely to increase if they have an unstable relationship with their primary caregivers. Furthermore, it was stated that insecure attachment, characterised by a lack of emotional support from caregivers, can lead to an increased fear of neglect or abandonment and may cause children to interpret social cues more negatively and respond more aggressively to perceived rejection. According to Mellin (2008), rejection sensitivity is a recurring, individual trait that may contribute to the development of internalising disorders such as loneliness and depression and it can be best described as a personal vulnerability factor that increases the probability that an individual would experience feelings of loneliness in the presence of specific stressors. According to London et al. (2007), rejection sensitivity is associated with loneliness and

adolescents who exhibit defensive affect (anxiety or rage) in situations when rejection is a possibility are more prone to certain forms of maladjustment, including social anxiety, withdrawal and violence towards others and may react to these signs in a variety of ways, such as internalising problems like depressive symptoms or exhibiting anxiety, anger, dependence or jealousy. The "rejection sensitivity dynamic combines a strong desire for more social provisions than one feels one has in any particular social situation with a bias towards underestimating the social provisions provided in that situation", which suggests that rejection sensitivity and loneliness are related (London et al., 2007). However, loneliness is difficult to quantify and understand using only quantitative measures due to its complex character (Lauder et al., 2004). It is characterized by the lack of significant social connections rather than the size of an individual's social network (Tanskanen & Anttila, 2016). Divisions can lead to loneliness, as in the case of a loved one moving away or becoming unavailable for play, leaving behind friends who are left stranded (Asher & Paquett, 2003). While one person may have few social contacts but be happy with them and not feel lonely, another person may have many social contacts and yet feel lonely if these interactions are considered unfulfilling. According to Peplau and Perlman (1982), psychological characteristics like anxiety, fear of rejection and lack of social skills are the causes of loneliness. Man being a social animal requires other people around him. Lack of social interaction and peer victimisation are responsible for loneliness among adolescents (Goswick & Jones, 1982). Building upon the connection between rejection sensitivity and loneliness, the purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between rejection sensitivity and adolescents' perceptions of loneliness, with an emphasis on gender differences. Understanding these trends might help identify individuals who are more vulnerable and promote their mental health.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the gender differences in rejection sensitivity and perceived loneliness among adolescents.

Author Note

Gurleen Kaur Bajwa, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab
Dr. Asha Chawla Thakral, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab
Dr. Deepika Vig, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab
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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Gurleen Kaur Bajwa, Department of Human Development and Family Studies, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab
E-mail: kgurleenbajwa16@gmail.com

- To find out the relationship of rejection sensitivity with perceived loneliness.

Method

Participants

The study was conducted on a sample of 460 adolescents (16-18 yrs) enrolled in 11th and 12th grades in the Government Senior Secondary Schools of three districts, namely Ludhiana, Patiala and Sangrur of Malwa region of Punjab. A complete list of all the Government Senior Secondary Schools was downloaded from the official website of the District Education Officer. The sample was equally divided across two genders (girls $n_g=230$ & boys $n_b=230$).

Measures

Self-structured Personal Information Sheet: Data on the socio-personal characteristics of the adolescents were gathered using a self-structured socio-personal characteristic information sheet. This sheet contained information about the adolescents' grade, gender, locale, parents' education and occupation, family size, family type, number of siblings and birth order.

Fear of Rejection Scale: Rejection sensitivity among selected adolescents was assessed by using the Fear of Rejection Scale developed by Nafees and Jahan (2018). This scale consists of three dimensions namely exclusion, rejection sensitivity and people pleasing. Overall, there were 15 statements in the questionnaire of which 14 were positive and 1 was negative. The participants recorded their responses on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Never to Always. Cronbach's Alpha scores for the scale ranged from 0.68 to 0.89 for the subscales and 0.79 for the entire scale, showing strong reliability and good internal consistency. The scale demonstrated good construct validity, confirming that it effectively measures fear of rejection among adolescents.

Score Range for Fear of Rejection Scale

S.No.	Levels of Fear of Rejection	Range of Raw Scores
1	Low	<36
2	Moderate	36-54
3	High	>54

Loneliness Scale: Loneliness Scale developed by Hamid and Parvez (2020) was used to assess the level of loneliness as perceived by adolescents. The scale consists of five dimensions; social relationship, interpersonal relationship, distressed reaction, social isolation and emptiness. It is comprised of 34 statements, including 14 positive and 20 negative. A five-point Likert-type scale ranging from Never to Always was used to record responses. The scale demonstrated strong reliability with a split-half dependability of 0.83 and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.87. Strong construct validity of the scale was demonstrated by significant correlations between dimensions at the 0.01 level.

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Score Range for Loneliness Scale

S.No.	Levels of Fear of Rejection	Range of Raw Scores
1	Low	<99
2	Moderate	99-130
3	High	>130

Pre-testing: The tools were translated into Punjabi vernacular to facilitate better understanding among the respondents. The questionnaires were pretested on 20 non-sampled students. Ten students from 11th grade (5 girls & 5 boys) and ten from 12th grade (5 girls & 5 boys) were randomly selected and given the Punjabi versions of the questionnaires. The final sample did not contain these students. The pre-test results demonstrated consistency, suggesting that the students gave credible answers.

Statistical Analysis

Various statistical tools were employed, including frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test, Z-test, and Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Data Collection

A total of 460 adolescents were selected, ensuring equal representation of girls and boys. Before the instruments were distributed, the participants were informed of the purpose and significance of the study. They were assured that the information collected would only be used for research purposes and their identities would remain confidential. In order to ensure the accuracy of the information, they were also urged to keep their responses private. The collected data was filled on the MS-excel sheet and was analysed with the help of SPSS23 software.

Results

Socio-personal Characteristics of the Respondents

The details of socio-personal characteristics of the adolescents as per their gender are shown below:

Table 1

Socio-personal Characteristics of the Adolescents as Per their Gender (n=460)

Socio-personal characteristics	Girls ($n_g=230$)		Boys ($n_b=230$)	
	f	%	f	%
Grade	117	50.87	115	50.00

	12th	113	49.13	115	50.00
Father's Education	Illiterate	26	11.30	34	14.78
	Primary	33	14.35	24	10.43
	Middle	47	20.43	37	16.09
	High School	71	30.87	87	37.83
	(+2) Intermediate	36	15.65	35	15.22
	Graduation	16	6.96	13	5.65
	Post-Graduation	1	.43	0	0.00
Mother's Education	Illiterate	47	20.43	48	20.87
	Primary	41	17.83	38	16.52
	Middle	43	18.70	43	18.70
	High School	53	23.04	54	23.48
	(+2) Intermediate	25	10.87	32	13.91
	Graduation	14	6.09	14	6.09
	Post-Graduation	7	3.04	1	.43
Father's Occupation	Service (Govt./ Private)	47	20.43	42	18.26
	Business	32	13.91	42	18.26
	Farming	24	10.43	23	10.00
	Labourer	96	41.74	102	44.35
	Any other (Vendor, Driver, Gardener, etc.)	31	13.48	21	9.13
Mother's Occupation	Service (Govt./ Private)	33	14.35	26	11.30
	Business	8	3.48	5	2.17
	Farming	2	.87	0	0.00
	Labourer	36	15.65	15	6.52
	Homemaker	136	59.13	166	72.17
Family Size	Any other (House-help, Laundry worker etc.)	15	6.52	18	7.83
	Small (upto 4 members)	84	36.52	108	46.95
	Medium (5-8 members)	134	58.26	108	46.96
Family Type	Large (9 and more members)	12	5.22	14	6.08
	Nuclear	70	30.43	56	24.35
	Joint	160	69.57	174	75.65
No. of Siblings	None	9	3.91	9	3.91
	One	102	44.35	105	45.65
	Two	81	35.22	81	35.22
	Three	31	13.48	24	10.43
	Four or more	7	3.03	11	4.77
Birth Order	First	101	43.91	92	40.00
	Second	93	40.43	88	38.26
	Third	29	12.61	38	16.52
	Fourth or above	7	3.04	12	5.22

Figure 1

Grade of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 2

Father's Education of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 3

Mother's Education of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 4

Father's Occupation of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 5

Mother's Occupation of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 6

Family Size of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 7

Family Type of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 8

No. of Siblings of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Figure 9

Birth Order of the Adolescents as per their Gender

Grade: Among girls, 50.87 percent were in the 11th grade and 49.13 percent were 12th graders. 50 percent of the students in grades eleven and twelve were boys. This proved that the sample was fairly represented and that there was an equal distribution of students among both genders.

Father's Education: When comparing fathers' educational attainment by gender, it was found that the majority of fathers of both girls and boys had a high school education, with a greater percentage of fathers of boys (37.83%) than fathers of girls (30.87%). Next in line was middle school education, which was more common among girls' fathers (20.43%) than among boys (16.09%). A higher percentage (14.35%) of fathers of girls had finished primary school education as compared to that of boys (10.43%). Illiterate fathers were more common among boys (14.78%) than among girls (11.30%). The percentage of fathers of both genders in the graduate

and post-graduation category of education was quite small, but the percentage of fathers of girls (15.65%) and boys (15.22%) with intermediate education was somewhat similar.

Mother's Education: For both genders, mothers' highest degree of education was high school, with 23.48 per cent of mothers of boys and 24.04 per cent of mothers of girls having completed high school. Mothers of boys (20.87%) and mothers of girls (20.43%) were nearly equally illiterate. There was no gender-based variance in the 18.70% middle education rate for either category. Following primary schooling were 17.83 per cent of mothers of girls and 16.52 per cent of mothers of boys. At the intermediate level, boys' mothers were more represented (13.91%) than mothers of girls (10.87%). In terms of graduation, mothers of both boys and girls had the same proportion (6.09%).

Father's Occupation: The data highlighted that a higher proportion of fathers of boys (44.35%) were found to be labourers as compared to fathers of girls (41.74%). Girls' fathers were more involved in business (13.91%) and services (20.43%) than fathers of boys (18.26%). Higher percentage of girls' fathers (13.48%) were found in other occupations (vendor, driver, gardener etc.) as compared to

that of boys (9.13%). Almost equal numbers of fathers of both genders worked in agriculture.

Family Size: A larger percentage of girls (58.26%) came from medium-sized families as compared to boys (46.96%). Boys were more likely to have small families (46.96%) than girls (36.52%). Boys were marginally more likely 6.08 per cent than girls to have large families (5.22%).

Family Type: While girls were more likely to have nuclear families (30.43%) than boys (24.35%), boys were more likely to have joint families (75.65%) than girls (69.57%).

Number of Siblings: 45.65 per cent of boys and 44.35 percent of girls had one sibling. 10 per cent of the boys and thirteen per cent of the girls had three siblings. The percentages of the two (35.22%) and no siblings (3.91%) categories were comparable for each gender. **Birth Order:** Findings revealed that girls (43.91%) were more likely to be the firstborn as compared to boys (40.00%). For girls, the percentage of second-born children was 40.43 per cent, while for boys, it was 38.26 per cent. Third (16.52%) and fourth or above (5.22%) birth orders were more common in boys (12.61%) than in girls 3.04 per cent.

Table 2

Gender-wise Distribution of Adolescents across Different Dimensions and Levels of Fear of Rejection (n=460)

Dimensions of Fear of Rejection	Levels	Gender				Z
		Girls (n _g =230)		Boys (n _b =230)		
		f	%	f	%	
Exclusion	Low	80	34.78	101	43.91	2.00*
	Average	145	63.04	125	54.35	1.89
	High	5	2.17	4	1.74	0.33
Rejection Sensitivity	Low	53	23.04	92	40.00	3.91**
	Average	132	57.39	124	53.91	0.75
	High	45	19.57	14	6.09	4.32**
People Pleasing	Low	75	32.61	108	46.96	3.14**
	Average	113	49.13	100	43.48	1.21
	High	42	18.26	22	9.57	2.69**
Overall Fear of Rejection	Low	45	19.57	84	36.52	4.04**
	Average	143	62.17	120	52.17	2.16*
	High	42	18.26	26	11.30	2.10*

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance *Significant at 5% level of significance

Figure 10

Gender-wise Distribution of Adolescents across Different Dimensions and Levels of Fear of Rejection

Exclusion: At the low level of exclusion, a significant difference ($Z=2.00, p<0.05$) was observed, with the percentage distribution of boys (43.91%) being higher than that of girls (34.78%). At the average level, there was no significant difference in the percentage of girls (63.04%) and boys (54.35%). A similar trend was followed at the high level.

Rejection Sensitivity: At low level, the percentage distribution of boys (40%) was significantly ($Z=3.91, p<0.01$) higher than that of girls (23.04%) in terms of rejection sensitivity. At average level, percentage of girls (57.39%) was higher than boys (53.91%) with no significant difference. At the high level, the percentage distribution of girls (19.57%) was significantly ($Z=4.32, p<0.01$) larger than that of boys (6.09%).

People Pleasing: Boys were significantly ($Z=3.14, p<0.01$) more

likely to be at low level of people pleasing (46.96%) than girls (32.61%). At average level, girls made up a larger percentage of the (49.13%) than boys (43.48%) with no significant difference. At high level, percentage of girls (18.26%) was significantly ($Z=2.69$, $p<0.01$) higher than boys (9.57%)

Overall Fear of Rejection: Boys' percentage distribution (36.52%)

was significantly ($Z=4.04$, $p<0.01$) higher than girls' (19.57%) at low level. At average level, significantly ($Z=2.16$, $p<0.05$) greater percentage of girls (62.17%) than boys (52.17%) showed an overall fear of rejection. Additionally, the proportion of girls (18.26%) was significantly ($Z=2.10$, $p<0.05$) higher than that of boys (11.30%) at the high level.

Table 3

Gender-wise Differences in the Mean Scores (\pm S.D) of the Adolescents across Different Dimensions of Fear of Rejection (n=460)

Dimensions of Fear of Rejection	Gender				t
	Girls (n _g =230)		Boys (n _b =230)		
	Mean	SD (\pm)	Mean	SD (\pm)	
Exclusion	17.12	3.57	16.58	3.94	1.52
Rejection Sensitivity	14.67	4.05	12.84	3.83	4.97**
People Pleasing	12.70	4.23	11.10	4.28	4.02**
Overall Fear of Rejection	44.40	9.37	40.47	9.58	4.44**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

Figure 11

Gender-wise Differences in the Mean Scores (\pm S.D) of the Adolescents across Different Dimensions of Fear of Rejection

The data put forth in Table 3 and Figure 3 depicted that exclusion, a dimension of fear of rejection, showed non-significant gender differences in mean scores. Girls (17.12 \pm 3.57) felt more excluded than boys (16.58 \pm 3.94). Similar trends were seen in rejection sensitivity, with girls (14.67 \pm 4.05) showing greater rejection sensitivity than boys (12.84 \pm 3.83), with significant differences ($t=4.97$, $p<0.01$). People-pleasing dimension of fear of rejection showed a significant difference in mean scores ($t=4.02$, $p<0.01$). Subsequent study revealed that girls (12.70 \pm 4.23) were viewed as more people-pleasers than boys (11.10 \pm 4.28). Similarly, a significant difference ($t=4.44$, $p<0.01$) was discovered in overall fear of rejection between girls (44.40 \pm 9.37) and boys (40.47 \pm 9.58). It was determined that, in contrast to boys, girls experienced a greater fear of rejection.

Table 4

Gender-wise Distribution of Adolescents across Different Dimensions and Levels of Loneliness (n=460)

Dimensions of Loneliness	Levels	Gender				Z
		Girls (n _g =230)		Boys (n _b =230)		
		f	%	f	%	
Social Relationship	Low	25	10.87	19	8.26	0.95
	Average	123	53.48	110	47.83	1.21
	High	82	35.65	101	43.91	1.81
Interpersonal relationship	Low	24	10.43	21	9.13	0.47
	Average	123	53.48	104	45.22	1.77
	High	83	36.09	105	45.65	2.08*
Distressed Reaction	Low	43	18.70	38	16.52	0.61
	Average	169	73.48	164	71.30	0.52
	High	18	7.83	28	12.17	1.55
Social Isolation	Low	36	15.65	33	14.35	0.39
	Average	188	81.74	168	73.04	2.22*

Emptiness	High	6	2.61	29	12.61	4.04**
	Low	27	11.74	17	7.39	1.58
	Average	123	53.48	102	44.35	1.95
Overall Loneliness	High	80	34.78	111	48.26	2.93**
	Low	24	10.43	15	6.52	1.50
	Average	133	57.83	105	45.65	2.61**
	High	73	31.74	110	47.83	3.52**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

Figure 12

Gender-wise Distribution of Adolescents across Different Dimensions and Levels of Loneliness

Social Relationship (SR): According to the findings, at low level of social relationship, the percentage distribution of girls (10.87%) was higher than that of boys (8.26%). In a similar vein, girls' percentage distribution (53.48%) was higher than boys' (47.83%) at average level. At high level, there were more boys (43.91%) than girls (35.65%). There was no significant difference across any level of social relationship.

Interpersonal Relationship (IR): The data on interpersonal relationship indicated that there was a high percentage of girls (10.43%) as compared to boys (9.13%) at low level with no significant difference. While there was no significant difference between the percentage distribution of girls (53.48%) and boys

(45.22%) at the average level, there was a significant difference ($Z=2.08, p<0.05$) at the high level, showing that a larger percentage distribution of boys (45.65%) had better interpersonal relationships than girls (36.09%).

Distressed Reaction (DR): A greater proportion of girls (18.70%) were determined to be at a low level than boys (16.52%). At the average level, a similar pattern was observed, percentage distribution of girls (73.48%) being marginally higher than that of boys (71.30%). At high level, boys (12.17%) had a larger percentage than girls (7.83%). There was no significant difference in the percentage distribution of distressed reaction at any level.

Emptiness (EMP): The findings showed that, at low level, the percentage distribution of girls (11.74%) was higher than that of boys (7.39%) in the emptiness dimension of loneliness, with no significant difference. At the average level, a similar pattern was observed with no significant difference, with girls (53.48%) having a higher percentage than boys (44.35%). The percentage of boys (48.26%) was significantly ($Z=2.93, p<0.01$) higher than that of girls (34.78%) at the high level, indicating that boys felt more emptiness than girls.

Overall Loneliness: The results in Table 4 and Figure 4 showed that, at low level, there was no significant difference in the percentage distribution of girls (10.43%) and boys (6.52%). The percentage of girls (57.83%) was significantly ($Z=2.61, p<0.01$) greater than that of boys (45.65%) at average level. With a significant difference of ($Z=3.52, p<0.01$), the percentage distribution of boys (47.83%) was higher than that of girls (31.74%), albeit at a high level.

Table 5

Gender-wise Differences in the Mean Scores (\pm S.D) of the Adolescents across Different Dimensions of Loneliness (n=460)

Dimensions of Fear of Rejection	Gender				t
	Girls (n _g =230)		Boys (n _b =230)		
	Mean	SD (\pm)	Mean	SD (\pm)	
Social Relationship	26.28	5.31	27.33	4.94	2.18*
Interpersonal Relationship	28.61	6.40	29.57	6.60	1.57
Distressed Reaction	17.58	3.93	18.90	4.01	3.54**
Social Isolation	21.42	3.83	22.20	4.64	1.97*
Emptiness	24.49	4.67	25.75	4.68	2.90**
Overall Loneliness	118.51	18.53	123.64	20.33	2.82**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

Figure 13

Gender-wise Differences in the Mean Scores (\pm S.D) of the Adolescents across Different Dimensions of Loneliness

The analysis in Table 5 and Figure 5 depicted the gender-wise differences in mean scores of adolescents across different dimensions of loneliness. Boys (27.33 ± 4.94) had significantly ($t=2.18, p<0.05$) better social relationship than girls (26.28 ± 5.31). Additionally, it was noted that boys (29.57 ± 6.60) had slightly better interpersonal relationship than girls (28.61 ± 6.40), but no significant difference was found. There were significant ($t=3.54, p<0.01$) gender differences in mean scores where boys (18.90 ± 4.01) exhibited a more distressed reaction than girls (17.58 ± 3.93). Additionally, it was shown that, with a significant difference in mean scores ($t=1.97, p<0.05$), boys (22.20 ± 4.64) felt more socially isolated than girls (21.42 ± 3.83). According to data on emptiness, a dimension of loneliness boys had significantly ($t=2.90, p<0.01$) higher mean scores (25.75 ± 4.68) than girls (24.49 ± 4.67). The mean scores of boys (123.64 ± 20.33) were significantly ($t=2.82, p<0.01$) higher than those of girls (118.51 ± 18.53) in terms of overall loneliness. It was determined that boys experienced more loneliness as compared to girls.

Relationship of Rejection Sensitivity with Perceived Loneliness among Adolescents

The illustration of data in Table 6 emphasized the correlation analysis between exclusion dimension of fear of rejection and various dimensions of loneliness among adolescents with reference to their gender.

Table 6

Relationship between Different Dimensions of Loneliness and Exclusion Dimension of Fear of Rejection among Adolescents as Per their Gender (n=460)

Dimensions of Loneliness	Exclusion	
	Gender (n=460)	
	Girls (n _g =230)	Boys (n _b =230)
Social Relationship	-.08	-.16*
Interpersonal Relationship	-.10	-.18**
Distressed Reaction	.11	.03
Social Isolation	.06	.26**
Emptiness	.14*	.18**
Overall Loneliness	.13*	.20**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

High levels of exclusion were also associated with higher levels of loneliness, according to the gender correlational analysis among

girls, which showed a significant positive correlation between exclusion and emptiness ($r=0.14, p<0.05$) and overall loneliness ($r=0.13, p<0.05$). Exclusion and no other aspect of loneliness were shown to be significantly correlated. However, among boys, there was a significant negative correlation between exclusion and social relationship ($r=-0.16, p<0.05$) and interpersonal relationships ($r=-0.18, p<0.01$), indicating that poorer interpersonal and social relationships were associated with more exclusion. On the other hand, exclusion was significantly positively correlated with social isolation ($r=0.26, p<0.01$), emptiness ($r=0.18, p<0.01$) and overall loneliness ($r=0.20, p<0.01$).

Table 7

Relationship between Different Dimensions of Loneliness and Rejection Sensitivity Dimension of Fear of Rejection among Adolescents as Per their Gender (n=460)

Dimensions of Loneliness	Rejection Sensitivity	
	Gender (n=460)	
	Girls (n _g =230)	Boys (n _b =230)
Social Relationship	-.08	-.17**
Interpersonal Relationship	-.03	-.32**
Distressed Reaction	.10	.24**
Social Isolation	.04	.21**
Emptiness	.13*	.20**
Overall Loneliness	.08	.28**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

In girls, there was no significant correlation found between rejection sensitivity and any dimension of loneliness except emptiness which had a significant positive correlation ($r=0.13, p<0.05$). Higher rejection sensitivity negatively impacted social and interpersonal relationships in boys, as evidenced by a significant negative correlation between rejection sensitivity and social relationships ($r=-0.17, p<0.01$) and interpersonal relationships ($r=-0.32, p<0.01$). Conversely, rejection sensitivity was significantly positively correlated with social isolation ($r=0.21, p<0.01$), emptiness ($r=0.20, p<0.01$), distressed reaction ($r=0.24, p<0.01$), and overall loneliness ($r=0.28, p<0.01$). These findings suggested that social isolation and loneliness were exacerbated by high rejection sensitivity.

Table 8

Relationship between Different Dimensions of Loneliness and People Pleasing Dimension of Fear of Rejection among Adolescents as per their Gender (n=460)

Dimensions of Loneliness	People Pleasing	
	Gender (n=460)	
	Girls (n _g =230)	Boys (n _b =230)
Social Relationship	.15*	.24**
Interpersonal Relationship	.13*	.31**
Distressed Reaction	.11	.19**
Social Isolation	-.06	-.31**
Emptiness	.16*	.25**
Overall Loneliness	.17**	.32**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

People-pleasing and social relationships ($r=0.15, p<0.05$), interpersonal relationships ($r=0.13, p<0.05$), emptiness ($r=0.16, p<0.05$) and overall loneliness ($r=0.17, p<0.01$) were significantly positively correlated among girls. Likewise, people-pleasing and social relationships ($r=0.24, p<0.01$), interpersonal relationships ($r=0.31, p<0.01$), distressed reactions ($r=0.19, p<0.01$), emptiness ($r=0.25, p<0.01$) and overall loneliness ($r=0.32, p<0.01$) were found to be significantly positively correlated in boys. However, social isolation was found to have a significant negative correlation with people pleasing ($r=-0.31, p<0.01$).

These findings suggested that pleasing others was associated with increased loneliness and strained relationships in both boys and girls, with the impacts being more pronounced in boys. Furthermore, despite feeling more distressed and emptier, boys who made more of an effort to satisfy others reported feeling less socially alienated.

Table 9

Relationship between Different Dimensions of Loneliness and Overall Fear of Rejection among Adolescents as Per their Gender (n=460)

Dimensions of Loneliness	Overall Fear of Rejection	
	Gender (n=460)	
	Girls (n _g =230)	Boys (n _b =230)
Social Relationship	-.12	-.23**
Interpersonal Relationship	-.10	-.34**
Distressed Reaction	.13*	.17**
Social Isolation	.02	.32**
Emptiness	.17**	.26**
Overall Loneliness	.15*	.33**

Note. **Significant at 1% level of significance, *Significant at 5% level of significance

Among girls, overall fear of rejection significantly positively correlated with distressed reaction ($r=0.13, p<0.05$), emptiness ($r=0.17, p<0.01$) and overall loneliness ($r=0.15, p<0.05$). Similarly, distressed reaction ($r=0.17, p<0.01$), social isolation ($r=0.32, p<0.01$), emptiness ($r=0.26, p<0.01$) and overall loneliness ($r=0.33, p<0.01$) significantly positively correlated with overall fear of rejection among boys which depicted that high fear of rejection increased loneliness. Although a significant negative correlation was observed between overall fear of rejection and interpersonal relationships ($r=-0.34, p<0.01$) as well as social relationships ($r=-0.23, p<0.01$).

Discussion

Gender Differentials in Rejection Sensitivity among Adolescents

Across both genders, it was determined that girls had more average and high levels of overall fear of rejection than boys, while a higher percentage of boys were at low levels across all dimensions and overall fear of rejection. Zulfiqar et al. (2024) also demonstrated that girls showed a more marked fall in psychological well-being as rejection sensitivity grew, whereas boys showed a greater psychological well-being and less rejection sensitivity. This disparity could be attributed to the culture being male-dominated and the society being patriarchal. Girls experienced a higher level of fear of rejection and became more sensitive to these negative social

interactions of social exclusion or rejection, which could have had a more significant effect on their mental health.

Exclusion was nearly identical, regardless of gender. Other dimensions, such as rejection sensitivity, people-pleasing and overall fear of rejection, showed a substantial difference, nevertheless. In addition to the other two aspects, it was revealed that girls had a much higher fear of rejection than boys. A study by Giovazolias and Paschalidi (2022) also indicated that girls were more likely to exhibit interpersonal anxiety and rejection sensitivity than boys. In general, girls were more likely to acquire anxiety disorders and appeared to have higher anxiety levels than boys. It was determined that the ability to build strong interpersonal ties may be hampered by both the expectation of rejection and the experience of rejection cues.

Gender Differentials in Loneliness among Adolescents

Both genders displayed varying degrees of loneliness, indicating that a greater percentage of boys had high levels of overall loneliness, while a higher percentage of girls experienced average levels of loneliness across all categories. It was determined that boys experienced a high degree of overall loneliness. According to a study by Cacioppo et al. (2009) girls were more likely to express negative emotions and show care for the feelings of others, but boys were more likely to stigmatize loneliness. The study also found that, despite potential measuring biases, girls reported loneliness more frequently than boys because they were able to identify such sentiments without experiencing as many social consequences. Furthermore, compared to girls, boys typically only expressed feelings of loneliness in response to many questions.

Significant differences were found in all dimensions except interpersonal relationship. Additionally, there was a significant difference between boys and girls in terms of overall loneliness, suggesting that boys experienced loneliness at a higher level. These findings were reinforced by a study that showed from adolescence onwards, boys experienced loneliness more often than girls. Although both boys and girls spent less time with their families, boys showed a steeper decline in family time than girls. It was shown that boys tended to isolate themselves more, whilst girls were better at expressing their emotions. It was found that spending more time alone increased the likelihood of loneliness in boys and worsened emotions of alienation from others during adolescence, a time marked by self-discovery and identity formation in relation to peers (Maes et al., 2019).

Assessing the Relationship of Rejection Sensitivity with Perceived Loneliness

Findings demonstrated that among both girls and boys, a greater fear of rejection was substantially linked to feelings of social isolation, loneliness, distressed reaction and emptiness. Distressed reaction, emptiness and overall loneliness were all significantly positively correlated with fear of rejection among girls. A similar trend was followed in boys as well. According to these findings, it was concluded that fear of rejection exacerbated higher levels of social difficulties and loneliness irrespective of gender. These findings were corroborated by a study by Lin and Fan (2023) which found a significant positive correlation between rejection sensitivity and loneliness. This implied that adolescents who displayed elevated rejection fear were more likely to experience emotional and social isolation. This correlation suggested that adolescents who had a

persistent fear of rejection were less likely to form or sustain social relationships because they often anticipated rejection or exclusion. The tendency to overinterpret vague or neutral social cues as signs of displeasure further strained already-existing relationships by undermining mutual understanding and trust. Their social networks consequently became more limited and unsupportive, which made them feel even more alone and perpetuated a downward circle of decreased social interaction and deteriorating relationships.

Conclusion

The current study established that, rejection sensitivity was significantly linked to perceived loneliness among adolescents with notable gender differences. Boys reported higher degrees of loneliness across a variety of dimensions, such as social isolation and emptiness, whereas girls showed higher levels of fear of rejection, particularly in the areas of rejection sensitivity and people-pleasing. Although the effect was more noticeable in some areas for boys, the correlation analysis showed a significant positive correlation that depicted both girls and boys with greater levels of fear of rejection were more likely to experience social difficulties, loneliness and distress. These findings emphasized the significance of addressing emotional vulnerabilities in adolescents, such as rejection sensitivity, to promote mental health and social well-being.

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